

Research Article

Identification of Criteria for Evaluating the Programmes and Activities of in School Youth Organizations in Agriculture in Ekiti and Ondo States Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

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The main purpose of the study was to determine the criteria for evaluating the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture using Ekiti and Ondo states as case study. The study was a survey research. A total of 770 respondents, purposively sampled from schools, Ministries of Education and Agriculture were used as subject for this study. The instrument used was 20 item questionnaire. Frequency distribution, mean, standard deviation, ranking order, t-test and ANOVA were used to analyze the data. The findings from the study show that evaluation of the programmes and activities of in school youth organizations in agriculture is inevitable for the purpose of programme and organization's improvement and feedback. Based on the finding's of this study, it was recommended among others that standard criteria should be set and reviewed regularly for use to evaluate the programmes of all in-school youth organizations in agriculture in secondary schools. It was also recommended that schools should publicize their activities and programmes through mass media, demonstrations and community development or shows.

INTRODUCTION

Evaluation is a significant component of any worthwhile agricultural education programmes and activities. Olaitan (1996) described evaluation as a process of focusing attention on the process of education using professional judgement and developed standard for education programmes. Similarly, Drucker (1977) emphasized that evaluation is a watchdog of programme management. It ensures that standard can be used for assessing programme performance and students productivity. Olaitan(1996) expressed that evaluation of agriculture programme in schools is a process of finding out how far learning experiences developed and organized are actually producing desired results in the organization and within students-members. He revealed that, the success of agricultural education programme is measured in terms of what has been learnt, and what changes the teaching-learning process has brought about within the students. He also emphasized that evaluation of the programmes of in –school youth organizations should be a continuous process.

In evaluating agricultural education programmes and activities in the school, Phipps (1980) suggested that the expected outcome should be carefully analyzed to determine the type of evaluation which would indicate that the objectives are being realized. He declared that the method developed for securing evidence which will reveal the degree to which both the student and the organization outcome are attained is called criterion. He defined criterion as established rules, standards or principles on which judgment is based. Olaitan (1996) observed that criteria for evaluating the programmes in agriculture may be slightly different from most of the research paradigms available in educational measurement, and evaluation. He expressed that the programmes in agricultural education have diverse objectives, design and implementation strategies. He remarked that evaluation of agricultural programmes is inevitable for the purpose of programme improvement.

Similarly, Uzockukwu (1996) asserted that evaluation of an in school youth programmes in agriculture in secondary schools should be a continuous process, that evaluation of school programmes must consist of efforts to improve programmes which were poorly designed, installed and poorly administered. He explained further that evaluation criteria must yield worthwhile data which should be useful to give a comprehensive picture of the student's development, appraise the effectiveness and difficulties which the student encounters through his school experience so as to provide for programme improvement. Olaitan (1996) therefore suggested that each component of the agricultural programmes should be separately evaluated.

Developing a criterion for evaluation of on-going programme in schools, Provus (1972) upheld that the following must be used to evaluate whether to improve, maintain or to terminate a programme (1) experts agreeing upon programme standard (2) determining

whether a discrepancy exists between some aspect of the programme and the standard governing the aspect of the programme. (3) using discrepancy information to identify the weakness of the programme. According to Provus, it is generally necessary for those concerned with the conduct of education to employ problem solving techniques once the weakness of the programme has been identified.

It has been observed that youths in secondary schools do not regard the current activities and programmes in agriculture as those that can prepare them for skill development and employment in agricultural occupations (Olaitan, 2010). This conception might have been responsible for low agricultural productivity and mass unemployment rate among school leavers in Nigeria. In an effort to address the downward trends in skill development through the activities and programmes of agricultural science in schools, it becomes necessary to determine the criteria that can be employed to evaluate the programmes and activities of in school youth organizations in agriculture, for programme and organization improvement purpose.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the following:

- 1) Agency or agencies to evaluate the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture in Ekiti and Ondo states.
- 2) Criteria to be used to evaluate the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture in Ekiti and Ondo states.

Hypothesis

There is no significant differences in the main rating of the responses of teachers of agriculture science based on their years of experience on the criteria for evaluating the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture in Ekiti and Ondo states.

Methodology

The design of the study was a survey research method. The study covered Ondo and Ekiti States of Nigerian made up of thirty four (34) Local Government Areas.

The population for this study consisted of 470 teachers who were presently the total number teaching agricultural science in the 350 secondary schools in Ondo and Ekiti States, 200 principals of the schools offering agricultural science, and 60 officials of the Ministry of Education, directly in-charge of secondary school agricultural science programmes. Also, included were the 10 officials of the Board for Vocational Technical Education and 30 officials of the Ministry of

Agriculture and ADP who are knowledgeable in youth clubs. The total population for this study was 770. The purposive sampling technique was employed to determine the sample for this study: Meaning that all the 770 teachers of agriculture and Ministry officials in the population were used for the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

Two structured questionnaires were used for collecting data for this study. The first questionnaire was meant for the administrators that is, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Agriculture/ADP, Board for Vocational Technical Education officials, principals with background in agriculture and Head of Agricultural Science Department. The second questionnaire was meant for teachers of agriculture. The questionnaires had 20 items. The respondents were requested to indicate their degree of agreement or disagreement with each of the

items in the questionnaire, The study made use of face and content validation. Reliability of the instrument was established by a test-retest reliability method to measure the degree of consistency the instrument demonstrates. Respondents opinion were subjected to reliability analysis using Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Co-efficient. The correlation Co-efficient (r) ranged from 0.834 to 0.987.

Method of Data Collection

To facilitate the administration of the instrument, the questionnaire was administered on the respondents by personal contact. In view of the large geographical study area, three research assistants were employed to personally administer the questionnaire by hand on the respondents, and collect back after completion. Out of the 770 questionnaire distributed to the respondents, 608 copies were returned and dully completed representing a 78.96 percent return rate,

Table 1: Distribution of Questionnaire to Respondents

S/N	Respondents	No Distributed	No Collection
1	Teachers of Agricultural Science	470	335
2	Principals, Vice principals and Head of Department	200	194
3	Ministry of Education Officials	60	46
4	Ministry of Agriculture/ADP officials	30	23
	Board for Vocational Technical Education Officials	10	10
	Total	770	608
Percentage Return rate = 78.96%			

Data Analysis

Data collected for this study were scored using the liker type of five point rating in which 5 = Strongly Agree, 4 = Agree, 3 = Undecided, 2 Disagree, 1 = Strongly Disagree. All the options were scored in the same direction. Frequency distribution, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and ranking order were employed to answer the research questions, t-test and Analysis of

Variance (ANOVA), were used to test the hypotheses in the study.

Research Questions 1

Which of the Government agency or agencies should evaluate the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture in Secondary Schools?

Table 2: Mean ranking of agencies to evaluate the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture in secondary schools.

	Agencies to evaluate Programmes and activities of the organization	TEACHERS of AGRIC SCIENCE N=335		ADMINISTRATOR N=273		REMARKS
		1	RANKING	X	RANKING	
a.	Board for Vocational Technical Education	4.84	1	4.35	2	Agree
b.	Teachers of Agricultural Science/Education	4.69	2	4.29	3	Agree
c.	Retired teachers of Agriculture	3.91	5	4.06	6	Agree
d.	Principals/VPs/Experienced HODs	3.94	4	4.22	4	Agree
e.	Agriculture Business-man	3.68	7	3.86	7	Agree
f.	Integrated efforts of different agencies	4.25	3	4.45	1	Agree
g.	Representatives of Ministry of Agriculture	3.77	6	4.17	5	Agree
h.	Community	3.56	8	3.73	8	Agree

Mean Ranking = $\frac{5 \ 4 \ 3 \ 2 \ 1}{\text{High } \beta \text{ à Low}}$

Results presented in Table 2 revealed the respondents degree of agreement with the 8 items. The mean ratings of the respondents opinion are all above 3.49; the cut off point. The teachers of agricultural science ranked item 1 highest which states that the Board for Vocational Technical Education should evaluate the performance of the organization (mean $x=4.86$). The administrators ranked integrated efforts of different agencies (mean $x=4.45$) highest. On the other hand, the community was rated least by the respondent ($x = 3.569$, $x =3.73$) even

though they agreed that all agencies should be involved in evaluating the performance of the organizations.

Research Question 2

What criteria should be used to evaluate the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture in secondary schools?

Table 3: Means response of respondents opinions on criteria to be used to evaluate the programmes and activities in-school youth organization in agriculture in secondary schools.

	Criteria for evaluating the organization	TEACHERS OF AGRICULTURE N=335		Principal N = 194		BVTE N = 10		GRAND N = 539		REMARKS	
		X	SD	X	SD	X	SD	X	SD		
	Criteria for evaluating in-school youth agricultural organization should be based on:	Mean		Mean		Mean		Mean			
1.	Established standard and policies set by experts	4.33	0.67	4.57	0.43	4.62	0.75	4.51	0.62	Agreed	
2.	Level of achievement based on set objectives	4.42	0.63	4.09	1.05	3.94	0.96	4.15	0.88	Agreed	
3.	Number of students enrolled in the organization	3.79	0.94	4.67	0.79	4.14	0.69	4.20	0.88	Agreed	
4.	Number of students attending meetings regularly	3.71	0.99	3.67	1.11	3.91	1.03	3.76	1.04	Agreed	
5.	Progress of students on their supervised agricultural experience programmes	4.17	0.79	4.05	0.73	4.56	0.57	4.26	0.69	Agreed	
6.	How students follow their plan of work	4.21	0.71	4.63	1.92	4.17	0.96	4.33	0.86	Agreed	
7.	Level of acquired skills to enter occupation in agriculture	4.31	0.78	4.58	0.87	4.63	0.62	4.51	0.76	Agreed	
8.	Acquired approved techniques useful in future occupation	4.32	0.77	4.17	0.55	4.58	0.91	4.53	0.93	Agreed	
9.	How finance and funds are managed	3.98	0.85	3.93	1.02	3.87	1.54	3.93	0.81	Agreed	
10.	How often official procedure are used in meetings	3.79	0.94	3.85	0.75	3.74	0.98	3.79	0.89	Agreed	
11.	How accurate records are kept	4.47	0.74	4.09	0.67	4.79	0.41	4.44	0.61	Agreed	
12.	How often programmes are evaluated at chapter local and state contests.	4.40	0.80	4.34	0.44	4.24	0.79	4.33	0.68	Agreed	

Results presented in Table 3 revealed that the respondents agreed with all the 12 items, all the items obtained mean rating above the cut off point of 3.49 which correspond with agreement in the decision rule. 4 out of the 12 items showed a higher degree of agreement than the others. The respondents strongly agreed that criteria for evaluating

an in-school youth organization in agriculture should be based on

a. Acquired approved techniques useful in future occupation ($x = 4.53, SD=0.93$)

b. Level of acquired skills to enter occupations in agriculture $x = 4.51, SD = 0.76$

c. How accurate records are kept and ($x = 4.44; SD = 0.61$)

d. Established standards and policies set by experts. $X = 4.51; SD = 0.62$

On the other hand, item 4, number of students attending meetings was rated least ($x=3,76, SD=1,04$). It was observed that the relatively high standard deviation of the item appear to make the opinions of the respondents less acceptable.

Ho₁:

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of the response of teachers in agricultural science

based on their years of experience on criteria for evaluation the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture in secondary schools.

Table 4: Analysis variance (ANOVA) of the mean ratings of teachers of agriculture based on Year of experience on what should be the criteria for evaluating the activities and programmes of a viable school youth organization in agriculture in secondary schools.

SOURCES of VARIATIONS	SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARES	F.CAL	f	f TABLE	REMARKS
BETWEEN	128.59	2	64.29	2.707	0.0682	3.02	NS *
WITHIN GROUPS	7908.19	333	23.75				
TOTAL	8036.78	335	88.04				

Not significant at $P < 0.05$

The information contained in Table 4 revealed that the calculated F value of 2.71 is less than the critical F. Value of 3.02 at 2 and 333 degree of freedom and $P < 0.05$. The value indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the respondents with respect to their year of experience on what should be the criteria for evaluating the activities and programmes of viable in-school youth organizations in agriculture in secondary in Ekiti and Ondo State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Finding

The findings revealed the twelve (12) criteria that were rated by the respondents as essential for evaluating the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture in secondary schools. This findings is supported by (Phipps 1980 and Olaitan 2010) that all phases of youth organization programme should be evaluated based on the criteria established. In his own studies, Uzochukwu (1996) reported that evaluation procedures in youth organizations should be designed to measure changes in abilities in terms of the objectives developed. He further remarked that evaluation criteria must yield worthwhile data which would be useful to give a comprehensive picture of the students and organizations development, appraise the organizations effectiveness and difficulties which the students encountered in their learning experiences. The researcher observes that evaluation of youth organizations should be an inevitable process which is expected to be continuous to allow for appraisal, feedback, replanning and improvement.

The null hypothesis showed that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of the teachers based on their years of experience on what should be the criteria for evaluating the programmes and activities of in school youth organizations in agriculture in secondary schools in Ekiti and Ondo states. This finding is in agreement with (Olaitan 1996 and 2010) postulation that evaluation is a significant component of a worthwhile agricultural education programmes and activities in secondary schools.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study and the discussions that followed, the following conclusion are drawn.

1. Standard criteria should always be used to evaluate the programmes and activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture on regular basis
2. The Board for Vocational and Technical education and integrated efforts of teachers and other agencies should be involved in the evaluation of the activities and programmes of in school youth organizations in agriculture .
3. Evaluation of programmes and activities of in school youth organizations in agriculture is inevitable for the purpose of programme and organizations improvement.

Recommendations

The findings of this study showed that evaluation of the programmes and activities of in school youth organization in agriculture is inevitable and it should be on a continuous basis. In view of this findings it was recommended that

- 1) Evaluation of the activities and programmes of all in-school youth organizations in agriculture should be carried out frequently at the end of every activities, and at least annually by teachers, of agriculture, Board for Vocational technical Education and the State Schools Board in order to provide feedback for improvement purpose.
- 2) Standard criteria should be set and reviewed regularly for use, to evaluate the programmes of all in-school youth organizations in agriculture in secondary schools.

- 3) Workshops and seminars should be organized by the Ministry of Education, Board for Vocational and Technical Education, and the State University to train and retrain all teachers of agricultural education/science on the required pedagogy for skill development activities and programmes that should be adapted for effective teaching and learning process.
- 4) Workshops and seminars should also organized for teachers of agriculture on how to publicize the activities of in-school youth organizations in agriculture through agricultural shows demonstration, and agricultural career days,

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